

EIC COMMUNITIES

D2.1 CoPs: Governance structure and management - first version

WP2: Community and synergy building between EIC portfolios and projects.

Task 2.1. Establishment and management of COPs

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Introduction

The EIC Communities Project

The EIC COMMUNITIES objective is to increase both visibility and impact of the European Innovation Council (EIC)-funded projects by stimulating synergies and innovation breakthroughs. Furthermore, it aims to select, involve, and actively engage key stakeholders who have a vested interest in their activities and results, such as scientific innovators, policy makers, and industry leaders.

The project will create three thematic Communities of Practice (CoPs) in the CleanTech, Industry and Health sectors. Its aim is to co-create diverse online and physical activities, materials and tools that encourage multidisciplinary interactions among EIC projects. Working closely with EIC representatives and EIC Programme Managers (PMs), the project will pioneer new engagement practices and offer policy recommendations for research and innovation in the future of deep tech.

The ultimate goal is to propel future technologies and innovations, driving towards a more connected and innovative future for broad, diverse and gender-inclusive deep tech communities.

The initial version of this report is presented in this deliverable. The D2.1 “CoPs: Governance structure and management” is meant to constitute a framework for the governance and management of Communities of Practices. Subsequent releases, featuring updates on the governance and structure, will be an ongoing process. This document will be a living one and other updates are foreseen in M10 (June 2024), M20 (April 2025) and M30 (February 2026) in order to update the governance structure according to the assessed needs.

Background & Context

The community built around the European Innovation Council has united and is curating a wide range of deep tech projects and entrepreneurs with more than 5,500 quality-stamped companies, 408 innovation-driven research teams and 800 innovations, and more than 2,800 corporates, investors, procurers and many more business intermediaries and market experts (EIC Pilot Impact Report 2021).

Building communities around EIC themes and challenges, encouraging interactions among them, is crucial for the EIC ecosystem. These collaborative efforts involve high levels of teamwork and pushing innovation across EIC projects. Creating inclusive communities and connections among EIC topics is vital for research and promoting collaborations across different fields. It helps EIC Project Managers oversee projects effectively and adapt to changes in the scientific and industrial world.

The main goal of EIC Communities project (or CSA project) is to make EIC projects more visible and impactful. This means working together on online and offline activities, resources, and tools in three Communities of Practice (CoP): CleanTech, Industry, and Health. These

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structures are designed to support diverse communities centred on specific themes, promoting teamwork within and across EIC challenges. CoPs also give EIC Project Managers a solid support and a good plan to build networks around these themes. In the end, these efforts will lead to new ideas about future technologies and important suggestions to keep deep-tech projects moving forward.

This report explains how to set up and run a CoP effectively. It involves careful planning, helping, and ongoing support. It is meant to be a living report to be refined over the duration of the project.

Purpose & Scope of a CoP

A CoP is a collective formed by individuals sharing common interests with the objective to learn, exchange knowledge, and refine their expertise within a specific field or domain. It aims to cultivate an environment that encourages sharing experiences, best practices, and insights among its members, thereby contributing to their collective growth and development.

In building a CoP, it is essential to define the common objectives, its scope and maintain focus. The scope of the CoP was defined in the CSA project proposal and further refined in the co-creation workshop, that took place in Brussels on 23rd October 2023 benefitting from the contribution of EIC Programme Managers (EIC PM) and project's partners. It sets the specific domains each CoP emphasizes on, maintaining focus and relevance while ensuring that the identified topics are broad enough to encourage meaningful knowledge exchange, while they are not too narrow so that they can limit the knowledge exchange and learning. Moreover, bilateral meetings between CSA team and the EIC PMs grouped in CoP themes, held in M4, have helped the CSA team in this action of identifying the precise objective of each CoP and actions and activities to be managed to assure the sustainability of the CoPs. These bilateral meetings were meant to be a follow-up of the co-creation workshop held in Brussels, to strengthen the relations with the EIC PMs.

CoP members early in the co-creation process will agree on their CoP objectives, they should maintain focus as it is crucial to avoid unrelated discussions while ensuring alignment with the CoP's objectives. This approach fosters purposeful exchanges and collaborations, leading to more impactful learning experiences. However, due to evolution of CoPs composition i.e. new funded projects, PMs that will leave and will be replaced, new objectives and scopes coming up and new trends or innovations, the CSA team is aware that some adaptability is needed during the CSA project lifetime, but always within the framework established in this document. This is done through constant evaluation and feedback mechanisms as they play a pivotal role in refining the co-creation process. This ongoing assessment seeks to enhance the CoP's effectiveness and ensure its continuous evolution to best serve its members.

Building the CoP

Building a CoP involves:

1. Surveying EIC PMs to select EIC-funded projects and identify needs and challenges for future networking and synergies.
2. Identifying crucial stakeholders with a vested interest in CoPs and subsequently assessing them.
3. Designing co-creation workshops and implementing them in order to build the CoP objective, activities and follow-up along with its members.

Identification & Engagement of CoP Members:

Building a successful CoP begins with identifying its key audience. Understanding distinct groups and their roles, interests, needs, contributions, and potential impact within the EIC ecosystem is crucial. This goes beyond the beneficiaries of the selected projects and will be part of the stakeholders mapping process which will unfold as per the below:

- Initial stakeholder identification that occurred during proposal writing phase
- The EIC PMs will communicate a list of stakeholders for the mapping process, enhancing the co-creation process.
- Review and validation during the co-creation workshop and supplemented with inputs from EIC PMs, they will indicate the project that they want to qualify for each CoP.
- Development of a comprehensive co-creation process (workshops, surveys, desk research, etc.)
- Exploring networks and initiatives of project partners APRE, EurA, and EBN, that have extensive connections with stakeholders.
- Identification of CoP members will be extended through the organization of 'open calls' relayed and promoted through the project communication channels.

Once the stakeholders are identified, strategic engagement enhances outcomes and ensures alignment with CoP objectives. The tailored engagement strategies for each stakeholder group will be developed by project partners. This could entail utilizing diverse communication channels, organizing events, fora, or platforms catering to each group's preferences.

Categories within CoP Members:

CoP Members can be categorized, and they would include:

- EIC Project Participants: Directly engaged individuals in EIC-funded projects, such as researchers, innovators, entrepreneurs, scientists, engineers, etc.
- EIC Project Stakeholders: Beyond participants, those with interests in EIC project, including policymakers, government representatives, industry leaders, investors, etc.
- Industry and Corporate Representatives: Companies interested in partnering or collaborating with EIC projects, including established corporations, startups, or industries seeking innovation opportunities.

- Investors and Funders: Entities offering financial support or investment opportunities for EIC projects, like venture capitalists or funding institutions.
- Research Institutions and Academia: Involved in collaborative research, knowledge exchange, or providing expertise to EIC projects.
- Government and Regulatory Bodies: Overseeing or regulating aspects related to the projects, including compliance, standards, or policymaking.
- Entrepreneurial Ecosystem: Providing resources, mentorship, or guidance to startups involved in EIC projects, such as incubators, accelerators, or innovation hubs.

Key Attributes of CoP Management:

Ownership & Commitment

Ownership and commitment are important attributes in the effective management of a CoP. Ownership comes with a sense of responsibility and accountability among members. When individuals within the CoP take ownership of their roles and contributions, they actively engage, share knowledge, and drive initiatives forward. Also, commitment, should be ensured with sustained participation. This establishes the groundwork for continuity, enabling the CoP to evolve and remain relevant over time.

Building Relationships:

A fundamental aspect of CoPs is nurturing relationships among members. This involves encouraging dialogue, active listening, and inclusive decision-making. Having a collaborative approach that ensures members feel valued and part of the CoP's journey, using co-creation, mutual learning, and shared goals.

Feedback, Adaptation, and Fine-tuning:

Continuous feedback, adaptation, and fine-tuning within the described framework are crucial elements in CoP development. Regular evaluation, post-meetings or post-events, periodic surveys, and specific thematic co-creation sessions engage CoP members effectively. Understanding the changing nature of stakeholder's involvement is important as their roles might change due to various factors such as organizational changes or loss of interests and loss of value perceived from participating in the CoP. Therefore, adaptation to the CoPs needs is key to maintaining an inclusive and responsive CoP, but always following the scope described in this document.

CoP Engagement & Facilitation

CoP Members Engagement

In recruiting members for a CoP an approach focused on creating a diverse and inclusive community should be considered:

- **Consider diversity:** To identify potential members, it's important to emphasize diversity in roles, experience levels, and perspectives. In practice, each CoP will begin by defining the member profiles and the desired number of individuals in each category to ensure a well-balanced group.
- **Articulate the value proposition of the CoP:** in other terms 'what's in it for them?', what are the benefits in participating at an individual level but also at an organisational/institutional one. This is essential to secure future commitment and ownership from the members.
- **Target the outreach:** Project partners along with EIC PMs will engage in targeted outreach through various channels, including industry forums, professional networks, social media platforms, and specialized publications within the CoP's domain. Customized messaging tailored to specific profiles encourages their active participation.
- **Leverage existing connections:** Project partners along with EIC PMs will leverage existing partnerships with relevant organizations in identifying potential members. Additionally, a referral process involving collaborating entities recommending or nominating suitable candidates for CoP membership has proven highly valuable in previous initiatives.
- **Networking:** Participation in industry events, workshops, and conferences as well as online platforms events related to CoP topics provides networking opportunities to connect with potential members. Identifying these events through industry-specific online platforms or social media communities helps target professionals interested in CoP activities.
- **Collecting data:** Through surveys, needs assessments, informational sessions, and webinars about CoP goals and membership benefits encourages potential members and their engagement.

In concluding this section, partners should ensure diversity in outreach efforts by targeting various demographics, sectors, geographic regions, and professional affiliations to build a well-rounded CoP with diverse perspectives. With all the methods mentioned, the CoP aims to attract a diverse range of members, contributing varied roles, experiences, and perspectives, thereby enriching the community, and having a dynamic exchange of knowledge and ideas.

CoP Leadership & Facilitation

An essential component in managing successfully a CoP is the leadership and facilitation skills. To ensure effective guidance, EBN has selected EBN team members and appointed

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managers for each CoPs, they will be supported by a 'technical expert' from the EBN Special Interest Groups (<https://ebn.eu/special-interest-groups/>). The facilitator/CoP managers, selected based on their prior experience in managing Special Interest Groups (SIGs), bring a wealth of expertise in fostering collaboration, facilitating discussions, and driving initiatives that align with the CoP's objectives. The appointed facilitators have previous experience in managing the SIGs. They have project management experience in sectors such as circular economy, space, industry, sustainability, social entrepreneurship, etc. They act as the main focal point and work together with the SIG chair, considered as the 'technical expert'.

The CoP Manager holds **essential responsibilities**:

- Guiding the CoP members in meeting the set objectives
- Ensuring that the CoP remains aligned with its purpose and objectives.
- Overseeing the relevance of planned activities
- Facilitating and moderating sessions/meetings
- Fostering an environment of collaboration and knowledge exchange
- Overseeing the development of a complete calendar of activities and community building activities
- Ensuring the proper communication with the CoP and beyond (across CoPs)
- Ensuring the proper collection of feedback and evaluation mechanisms from the CoP stakeholders
- Making sure members remain engaged and keep on participating in activities. Enquiring for lack of involvement from members.
- Addressing any issues or challenges that may arise within the CoP.
- Communicate and refer monthly to the CSA project coordinator (APRE)

In the future, and upon building the CoPs, community guidelines for CoP communication will be developed, setting clear expectations and norms for interaction. These guidelines will outline communication protocols, respectful engagement, sharing practices, inclusivity considerations, and confidentiality measures, fostering an inclusive and productive atmosphere for the CoP's growth and collaboration. The communication strategy will also be defined at later stages, building upon the stakeholder's mapping, needs assessment and co-creation activities.

Regarding **the CoP manager/ facilitator soft skills**, they must/should:

- Demonstrate effective communication skills and active listening.
- Have strong moderation skills, ensuring inclusive engagement among all CoP members.
- Adapt to changing needs given the evolving nature of the CoP, while adjusting the objectives if needed, aligning with membership dynamics, and with industry trends.

In conclusion, effective leadership and facilitation are not just about steering the CoP, but about cultivating an environment that thrives on collaboration, learning, and adaptation.

Activities within the CoPs

Workshops & Meetings

The CoP manager, in collaboration with various stakeholders, should carefully consider the design and implementation of CoP activities, taking into consideration several factors such as member's needs and interests, providing value, engagement strategies, evaluation mechanisms, and inclusivity. Activities will revolve around some main formats:

- **Needs Assessment:** an essential first component needed to identify gaps and requirements within a specific context. It ensures that the project partners are aligned with the initial needs of the project. A needs assessment was conducted in the first months and was intended at supporting the selection of EIC projects and devising a strategy to engage EIC PMs in the CSA project. The CSA team actively encouraged the direct participation of EIC PMs and other representatives in a dedicated co-creation workshop held in Brussels on October 23, 2023, as outlined in the DoA. During this workshop, EIC PMs were invited to discuss the status, strengths, challenges, and obstacles encountered in supporting the existing set of selected projects. They also shared their vision for developing CoPs within the CSA project. The co-creation process included further desk research; feedback forms, surveys, interviews with key stakeholders. The findings of this needs assessment are found in D1.1. In conclusion, the insights gathered from the EIC PMs are crucial in refining the selection and organization of EIC thematic and challenge-driven portfolios and associated projects earmarked for CoPs.
- **Co-creation Workshops & Kick-off Meeting:** the CSA team will initiate the CoP journey with 3 co-creation workshops and a kick-off meeting. This serves as a starting point to introduce CoP members, outlining expectations, goals, and guidelines. The co-creation workshop encourages active participation from members, encouraging collaboration in defining the CoP's objectives, structure, and strategies. The kick-off meeting sets the tone for the CoP's purpose, promoting a shared understanding and commitment among members. More specifically, the online co-creation workshops (3) will be organized in February 2024. They will gather beneficiaries of all projects grouped in the respective CoPs, relevant EIC PMs and other CoP stakeholders (including investors, market experts, research and academia, entrepreneurial ecosystems, etc). Three co-creation workshops will be organized, each co-creation workshop will consist of:
 - a plenary session where the Project team will present the project, the CoP structures, and planned activities,
 - break-out sessions for each set of selected projects included in the CoP– to identify the specific needs and expectations towards the project and to tailor accordingly community and synergy building activities for each CoP.
- **Establishing Regular Meetings:** as consistency is key in maintaining CoP momentum. Establishing a regular meeting schedule ensures ongoing engagement and progress. These meetings, aligned with the CoP's Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), provide a platform to review progress, discuss challenges, and reassess strategies. This regular pace fosters accountability and allows for the timely adjustment of activities to meet defined objectives.

- **Thematic Webinars and Skill Development:** facilitating skill development and learning opportunities is key within a CoP. Members benefit from accessing resources that enhance their skills relevant to the CoP's domain. To achieve this, the CoP can connect members with relevant thematic webinars, workshops, or industry-specific courses. Additionally, organizing skill-focused sessions within the CoP or inviting experts for specialized webinar further enriches members' skill sets. Collaborations with educational institutions or industry partners part of EBN network can provide access to specialized courses.

Typical activities to be conducted within CoPs

- **Online meetings:** Biannual online meetings will take place with EIC PMs to align on their expectations versus the project and the development of a sustainable EIC community model.
- **Online pitching sessions (2):** where EIC project representatives will have the opportunity to pitch their project activities and results. This will promote sharing of best practices as well as access to potential investment opportunities, links to corporate or industries and will indirectly benefit the projects. EIC project will receive exposure through the communication channels.
- **Online thematic webinars/workshops (2):** this is part of building the capacities of projects. The specific topics will be identified in the co-creation sessions as they need to answer the specific needs. They will be delivered by experts in the identified field. They can be related to business skills (building financial capacities, access to funding, etc.) or soft skills (presentation, pitching, etc.) or more scientific/technical subjects that are particular to those CoP members' needs.
- **Knowledge Exchange Sessions:** within a same CoP or across CoPs, bilateral exchanges (2) will be organised, and the results of that exchange will be translated in a case study that will be produced and disseminated.
- **Portfolio days (2):** (online) organised in each CoP, moderated by CoP managers with the support of technical experts, they will gather projects' beneficiaries (from EIC thematic and challenge-driven projects), PMs and EIC representatives as well as relevant CoP stakeholders. The detailed content will be subject to determination within the co-creation process; however, they should include:
 - Panel discussions on latest policy/regulatory insights and technological breakthroughs related to the CoP focus.
 - Latest achievements of each CoP set of selected projects.
 - Presentations of selected projects (objectives, latest results, research/exploitation needs, etc).
- **Information Days:** the CSA team will collaborate with the EIC to support the organization of the Information Days and involve the CoP members.

Content and Knowledge Sharing within the CoP

Within the CoP, sharing knowledge and insights is what keeps the momentum and the collaboration running. This section explores how exchange of information happens within the CoP, best practices, and the sharing success stories among members. This will be further assessed with the co-creation workshops where the tools and methods to be used

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to communicate effectively, encourage active participation, curate valuable resources, and celebrate achievements will be further identified. The following main points will be considered:

- **Selecting the right communication and collaboration platforms:** this is crucial for CoP members as there are various tools, from emails to comprehensive online platforms like Slack, offer different functionalities. Careful consideration should prioritize accessibility and acceptance among CoP members, as resistance to adopting essential platforms may hinder efficient sharing of insights and resources. During co-creation workshops, dedicated channels will be identified and defined for each activity, utilizing diverse formats to accommodate different preferences.
- Implementing a **Knowledge Management System** is important where relevant articles, books, resources, and case studies are curated in a user-friendly repository categorized by themes, topics, or expertise areas. Regular updates maintain its relevance, encouraging continuous learning and informed decision-making among members.
- Finally, the CoP serves as a platform to **recognize and showcase achievements and success stories** as emphasized by PMs. This will be done through the DeepSynC platform, to celebrate accomplishments, acknowledge contributions, and inspire others within the CoP. Sharing success stories not only motivates and educates members but also transforms the DeepSynC platform into a vibrant hub for knowledge exchange, collaboration, and inspiration within the CoP.

Sustainability of the CoP:

Sustainability within a CoP is essential for its longevity and continued effectiveness beyond the project duration. Some tangible ways to address and ensure the sustainability of a CoP, are listed below:

- **Seeking feedback periodically:** CSA team will put in place mechanisms to collect inputs such as implementing a feedback mechanism to gather member's input on CoP activities. For instance, create a designated section on the CoP platform where members can submit suggestions or feedback.
- **Establishing a feedback loop for continuous improvement:** using automated surveys sent via emails after meetings or events to gather specific feedback and further analyse this feedback and incorporate suggestions for future activities. The members could rate the session content, delivery, and dynamics, provide comments, and suggest topics for future discussions. Based on the feedback it is essential to adapt the structure and activities accordingly.
- **Providing a continuous evaluation of the CoP performance:** by regularly assessing the CoP's effectiveness against predefined objectives, such as:
 - Members attendance: registration and attendance to the sessions
 - Members engagement: tracking the number of active participants in discussions.
 - Usage of the platforms: usage and contributions, monitoring the frequency of visits, downloads, or interactions with shared articles, resources, and case studies, etc.
- **Collaboration:** tracking the number of joint projects, cross-functional collaborations, or co-created resources, as well as instances of mentorship, networking, or peer-to-peer support within the CoP.
- **Planning for sustainability and scalability from the outset:** Project partners will integrate from the co-creation process, considerations on how to design the CoP with the sustainability aspect in mind. It should consider how the CoP will grow and evolve beyond the project duration. For example, the plan could include strategies for accommodating a larger community, integrating new members, and diversifying activities as the CoP expands. At the same time, and of utmost importance identifying successors for key roles within the CoP to ensure continuity. This involves preparing individuals or nominating new ones who can step into important roles as the community grows. An example would be to designate experienced CoP members as mentors to newer members, gradually involving them in leadership roles and responsibilities until they are ready to exchange roles.

Conclusion

The EIC Communities Project aims to foster collaboration and innovation within the European Innovation Council's funded projects. By creating thematic CoPs in CleanTech, Industry, and Health sectors, this project aims to cultivate inclusive environments that facilitate multidisciplinary interactions, knowledge exchange, and innovative ideas.

Throughout this report, the framework for governing and managing these CoPs has been outlined, emphasizing the critical role of stakeholder engagement, defined objectives, and ongoing adaptability within the defined scope. The CoP's purpose, methodology, activities, and sustainability measures have been comprehensively detailed, highlighting the dedication to creating vibrant, long-lasting communities centred on innovation and cross-sector collaboration.

Moreover, the report emphasizes the importance of diverse and inclusive membership, active engagement strategies, and the leadership's commitment to nurturing an environment conducive to learning, feedback, and continuous improvement. It underlines the need for agility in response to evolving project dynamics, stakeholder roles, and industry trends, all while staying aligned with the CoP's defined scope.

The future path of these CoPs stands on the pillars of ongoing evaluation, active member participation, robust communication, and a keen eye on scalability and sustainability beyond the project's duration. As these communities evolve and expand, their success centres on adaptability, member-driven contributions, and the anticipation to prepare future members to ensure continuity and growth.

This report serves as a foundational roadmap for the effective governance, management, and sustainable growth of the EIC Communities of Practice.